

Clustered Logistic Regression Algorithm for Flight Delay Prediction

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Abstract—Cluster computing is a part High Performance Computing (HPC) which become more and more popular and necessary in the recent years. Meanwhile, data mining is a technology that have been growing where its huge benefits are inevitable. Once cluster computing and data mining are combined, it will yield a very powerful machine whereby the processing time in data mining can be accelerated by using the strength of cluster computing. The cost of developing cluster computing is also more efficient compared to buying a computer with very high specs such as server computer or even supercomputer. In this research, we present a simulation of cluster computing in virtual environment while implementing data mining algorithm to perform a prediction of flight delay. The aim of this research is to evaluate the performance improvement of logistic regression for doing the prediction in cluster environment. The result shows that cluster computing can significantly accelerate the computational speed of algorithm, compared to standalone mode. In this experiment, by using 1 master and 3 worker nodes (with identical hardware specifications), the computation time of logistic regression can be decreased up to 27.03%. Attaching more nodes to the cluster will lead to a better computation performance of cluster itself.

Keywords—Cluster computing, clustered logistic regression, logistic regression, flight delay prediction, pyspark, apache spark.

I. INTRODUCTION

One of the hottest topics in the computer fields for these recent years is High Performance Computing (HPC) [1]. There are 2 kinds of HPC, namely traditional HPC and Modern HPC. The most famous example of traditional HPC is supercomputer.

Meanwhile, modern HPC has 3 types, those are grid, cloud, and cluster computing [2]. Grid computing has advantages in term of load balancing, reliability and accessibility to the additional storage. Benefits of cloud computing are, it has a very huge power as is supercomputer, high resource availability, virtualization, flexibility, and crash recovery. Whereas cluster computing is suitable for the computation that needs single system image (SSI), manageability and high availability.

Those three types of computation have their own objectives [2], [3], [4]. All of them are able to process the same data, but

different in term of scale of data. Grid and Cloud computing are too overkill to process the simple data mining computation, in which cluster computing is enough for it. Given that the dataset which used in this experiment is not too large whereas the computation is quite simple, so cluster computing is suitable for it. Cluster computing can provide supercomputing power, but on a smaller scale. Cluster computing can process a data faster than standalone one. The more computer connected to the cluster, the more speed can be produced by them.

Commonly, data mining task is processed in the standalone environment. Mining a large dataset in the standalone computer is not effective since it takes so much time (could be hours or even days), depend on how large the dataset is, and how good the hardware is. A solution is needed to tackle this problem, so that computational time can be reduced significantly with minimum cost [4], [5].

In this research, we firstly build a cluster environment then perform data mining computation on it. The algorithm which used here is logistic regression. This algorithm is applied to predict the flight delay. The data is gathered from the public dataset. By using the same algorithm and dataset, we then compare the computation performance on 3 scenarios.

The first scenario is performing the computation in a standalone environment. In this step, we use a single virtual PC with 1 core CPU and 3 GB RAM. In the second scenario, we provide 3 virtual PC's in which 1 VPC serves as master node, and the rest 2 VPC's serve as worker nodes. Those 3 VPC's have the same configurations as the standalone one (1 core CPU and 3 GB RAM). Third scenario provide 4 VPC's, with 3 worker nodes. All the configurations are the same with the previous one. This simulation is conducted inside the virtual machine software, called VirtualBox (virtualbox.org).

To understand the power of cluster computing, we execute the same source code in 3 different scenarios. In each scenario, we repeat the process 5 times to get the average processing time. We then compare those 3 average processing time from those 3 scenarios. Through this experiment, we can clearly see the power of cluster computing in accelerating the mining speed of logistic regression algorithm.

This paper consists of six sections. Section I explains the introduction and background of study. Section II discusses some related researches that conducted by other researchers.

The methodology of this research is described in section III. Section IV presents the experiment process and result. In this section, logistic regression algorithm is implemented in both standalone and cluster environments. Conclusion of this research is discussed in the section V and followed by the future work in section VI.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

One of well-known types of superior computing or High Performance Computing (HPC) is Cluster Computing [1], [2]. Cluster computing is part of distributed or parallel processing in which it involves several nodes that connected to each other through Local Area Network (LAN) [1], [4]. Those connected computers works together to solve the given problems. By using such kind of computation, there are some benefits that can be obtained, such as: high availability, cost reduction, as well as manageability [1], [4], [6], [7].

According to [4], there are three types of cluster computing, those are: High Performance Computing Cluster (HPCC), High Availability Cluster (HAC), and Load Balancing Cluster (LBC). In this research, we focus on the first type of cluster computing, namely High Performance Computing Cluster. The main objective of HPCC is to accelerate the computing performance. In this research, HPCC is used to accelerate the computing performance for flight delay prediction.

Based on data from [8], around 20% of airline flights in the world arrive more than 15 minutes late. Flight delay can be detrimental to many parties, especially for passengers and airlines [9]. By this fact, it is necessary to develop a system for predicting flight delay, so that stakeholders can prepare some strategies to deal with this problem. Such system needs a good algorithm as well as robust infrastructure. This research provides a solution by implementing one of popular algorithm in classification, called Logistic Regression, to predict whether the flight will delay or not. To accelerate the computational time, we execute this algorithm in cluster environment by using PySpark.

The combination between data mining and cluster computing is known as distributed data mining [5]. Many papers have discussed about distributed data mining algorithm, such as: random forest [10]–[12], AdaBoost [10], Decision Tree [10], [11], [13], Naïve Bayes [14], C4.5 [14], KNN [10], Linear Regression [1], [11], [14], Gradient Boosting Classifier [15], Deep Learning [16], etc. In the previous research, we also have discussed a computation of clustered data mining algorithm by using one of the most popular clustering algorithm, linear regression [1]. We implemented linear regression algorithm on top of Spark to perform prediction of flight delay as well.

In this research, logistic regression is chosen because of its popularity for predicting an event according to specific pattern for the classification. Logistic regression has become one of important tool for data analysis, especially in the area of classification. This research is not focusing on the comparison of algorithm, but more to the comparison between cluster and standalone computing. The performance improvement with clustered computers will be calculated and compared to the standalone one, to see the efficiency that can be obtained with cluster environment.

III. METHODOLOGY

The details of experiment in this research are listed as follows:

- Algorithm: Logistic Linear
- Dataset: Flight (2702218 records, with 70% for training and 30% for testing)
- Number of nodes: 1-4 (using VirtualBox)
- A computer with specification: Intel Xeon E5620 Processor (Cores: 4, Threads: 8), 16 GB RAM, DDR5 4 GB VGA RTX 550, 3TB HDD, Windows 10 OS.

This simulation is conducted on top of virtual machine (VirtualBox). All the created nodes have the same specifications, such as: single CPU core, 3GB RAM, Windows 8.1, and PySpark as cluster computing platform. The dataset is downloaded from the internet and it is ready to use (already preprocessed).

Figure 1: 4 Virtual PCs are created in Virtual Machine with equal specifications

Apache spark was chosen because it is claimed more powerful, especially for cluster computation, compared to other competitors, such as Hadoop [1]. Spark was claimed 10 times faster than Apache Hadoop when perform processing in hard drive, but surprisingly it becomes 100 times faster when perform in-memory computing [1]. PySpark itself is a combination of python programming language and Apache Spark. This collaboration brings huge advantages, especially in the field of data science. Through PySpark, users can call python library and execute it on top of Spark.

IV. EXPERIMENT & RESULT

In this experiment, we performed the computation in 3 scenarios, those are:

- Standalone: it involves a single PC (in virtual machine) with 1 CPU core and 3GB RAM. No other PCs connected to this standalone PC.
- Cluster_1: it involves 3 PCs (in virtual machine) in which 1 PC serves as a master node and another 2 PCs serve as worker nodes. In addition, each PC has 1 CPU core and 3 GB RAM.
- Cluster_2: it involves 4 PCs (in virtual machine), each acquires 1 CPU core and 3 GB RAM. 1 PC serves as master node and 3 PCs serve as worker nodes.

In the first scenario, we firstly created the first node (Node_1) and execute the algorithm trough Jupyter Notebook. This first experiment was conducted in standalone mode. The result was, it took 169.4 seconds to complete the task (*Table 1*). We then repeated the execution process up to 5 times to gain the average computational time. In the standalone environments, the average computational time of this algorithm is 166.82 seconds.

No.	Environments	Computational Time (in seconds)					
		Experiment					Average
		1	2	3	4	5	
1	Standalone (3GB RAM)	169.4	166.2	169.3	161.9	167.3	166.82
2	Cluster_1 (2 workers) - @3GB	151.5	152.7	153	169.2	157.8	156.84
3	Cluster_2 (3 workers) - @3GB	129.9	114.8	128.6	118.2	117.1	121.72

Table 1: Results of computation performance between standalone and cluster computing

On the 2nd scenario, we used 1 master node and 2 worker nodes. The processing time became slightly faster compared to standalone computing. However, the decrease in computational time is not very significant. By involving 3 nodes in total, we took only 5.98% better performance than the standalone one.

On the 3rd scenario, we used 1 master and 3 worker nodes to increase the speed of computation. Here, we got significant result where the average processing time drop to 121.72. This performance is 27.03% better than standalone one.

We then repeated each scenario 5 times in order to obtain the average time for all computation environments. The average computational time for standalone, cluster_1, and cluster_2, are 166.82, 156.84, and 121.72 respectively (see Table 1).

According to the table 1, cluster computing can increase the processing speed as well as decreasing the computational time significantly. By creating a cluster environment with 1 master and 2 worker nodes (with identical hardware specifications), the computational time decrease up to 5.98%. After attaching 1 more node that serve as a worker, the computational time fall down up to 27.03%. This fact shows that more computer will lead to better performance result.

Figure 2: Computing time has continued to go down when more computers are connected

By these experiment, it proves that cluster computing is a good solution to improve the computational speed. The more computers attached to the cluster, the faster the computation speed. Commodity hardware is enough to accelerate the processing time. Once we found the unused PCs, then we can attach them to the system directly with little configuration, thanks for its scalability. Horizontal scalability is one of main advantages of cluster computing. However, better hardware attached will produce better performance on the cluster.

V. CONCLUSION

This research was performed to evaluate the performance of logistic regression algorithm to process the data in cluster environment. The flight dataset which used in this research was downloaded from github.com and considered as a public dataset. All the experiment in this research was conducted in virtual environment, by using VirtualBox. We provided 3 scenarios for the experiment, those are: standalone (1 virtual pc), cluster_1 (1 master and 2 workers), and cluster_2 (1 master and 3 workers). In each scenario, we executed the program 5 times and recorded the computational time. We then calculated the average time of each scenario as shown in Tabel 1. According to the experiment, by creating a cluster environment, the processing speed become faster, so that computational time is decreasing. 1 master with 2 worker nodes reduced the processing time up to 5.98%. But after attaching 1 more virtual PC (becomes 1 master and 3 worker nodes), the computation time drop up to 27.03%. It means that, to produce better result, we should attach more nodes or even with better hardware specifications.

VI. FUTURE WORK

As a future work, research in flight delay prediction will be conducted by using other machine learning methods and implemented on the cluster environment. The performance of those algorithms, later will be compared with logistic regression that already discussed in this paper, to find the best algorithm for the case of flight delay prediction.

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